

I.FAST

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MILESTONE REPORT

ORGANIZATION OF THE WORKSHOPS

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ABSTRACT

This report is summarizing the results of 4 workshops to facilitate collaboration between laboratories and external stakeholders, with a particular focus on specific types of Test Platforms (sub-task (13.2.3)).

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

This report provides an overview of Task 13.2, especially sub-task 13.2.3 within the framework of the I.FAST European project:

Sub-Task 13.2.3 (INFN): Organizing annual workshops to facilitate collaboration between laboratories and external stakeholders, with a particular focus on specific types of Test Particles (TP).

1 Introduction

Sub-Task 13.2.3: A fundamental aspect of our endeavour involved the organization of small workshops, each dedicated to a specific type of TP. These workshops brought together personnel from laboratories operating TPs of the designated type and potential users, including those from industry. The core purpose of these workshops was to introduce the TPs to potential users and elicit their feedback.

2 Workshops

Small workshops dedicated to a particular type of TP have been organized, which gather personnel from the labs operating TPs of this type and possible users. The aim of these workshops was to present the TPs to the possible users and identify how the services could be adapted or improved to better correspond to their expectations.

The subject and location of the workshops dedicated to particular types of TPs were as follows:

- SRF cavity testing at DESY, Hamburg
- Superconducting magnet test facilities at LASA Milano
- Platforms for characterization, treatments and test of materials at IJCLab, Orsay
- Facilities for beam test of accelerator components at IFJ PAN, Krakow.

2.1 SRF CAVITY TESTING WORKSHOP

The first workshop took place in DESY, Hamburg, on September 14 and 15, 2022 on (vertical) cavity testing.

The Program Committee for the workshop consisted of:

- Lea Steder / DESY (CHAIR)
- Andrea Lidl / INFN LNF (I.FAST WP13.2.3)
- Akira Miyazaki / Uppsala University
- Hans Weise / DESY (I.FAST WP13.2)
- Alan Wheelhouse / STFC
- Mateusz Wiencek / DESY (AMTF Test Stand Operation)

Target group was on one hand the group of colleagues from labs with testing infrastructure, and on the other hand project delegates, who need their cavities tested.

The complete workshop documentation with all the presentations is available through <https://indico.desy.de/event/35316>. Altogether 42 participants from 14 laboratories and industry joined the meeting. In total 11 contributions introduced the measurement infrastructures of the different labs, including all the actually planned upgrades concerning diagnostic and test systems, as well as test capacities. Projects described their needs and schedules for cavity testing.

The in-person discussions during the workshop were absolutely important, after the long Covid suffering break. The small workshop dinner was held right next to the DESY vertical test stands and followed directly the extended tour through the TF infrastructure.

List of SRF cavity test benches in Europe and its customers:

SRF cavity test benches in Europe	
Within AMICI & I.FAST	CEA Saclay
	CERN
	DESY
	IJCLab
	INFN LASA
	INFN Legnaro
	UKRI Daresbury
	Uppsala University
others	HZB Berlin
	HIM Mainz
	HZDR Dresden
	TU Darmstadt
	Uni Wuppertal ?
outside Europe	Cornell Univ.
	JLAB
	FNAL
	MSU
	TRIUMF
	KEK
	IHEP
	SARI
....	

Customers				
			service contracts	In-kind
Industry	Research Instr.	LCLS-II	DESY	
		ESS-HB	DESY	
		PolFEL	DESY	
	ZRI Zanon	ESS-MB		
	INFN	ESS-MB	DESY	ESS-MB

Institutes / projects		PIP-II	(DESY)	PIP-II
	STFC	ESS-HB PIP-II	DESY	ESS-HB
	ESS	HB & MB		
	SOLEIL			
	CERN	FCC		
	SLAC	LCLS-II HE	DESY	
	FNAL	LCLS-II HE PIP-II		LCLS-II
	JLAB	LCLS-II HE	DESY	LCLS-II
SARI	SHINE	DESY		

Conclusion:

The workshop brought together key experts from all respective Test Facilities. Closer contacts were established. In discussions between the labs and with institutes a much better understanding of TF capabilities and research project needs were gathered. During the weeks and months following, a more direct exchange between the partners became visible. The preparation of cavity testing related to future European and worldwide activities was clearly supported by the workshop.

2.2 SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNET TEST FACILITIES WORKSHOP

The SC Magnet Workshop was organized in order to create a platform for the community of SC Magnet, with the joint participation of Research Institutes and Industries, and to discuss the present exploitation of Technological Infrastructures (TIs) and the innovative projects that they host.

The aim of the two day workshop was the presentation of all the TI’s, which are already in operation at the European Institutes, the discussion of Industry needs in relation to their innovative projects and how these TI’s could be better exploited.

The first day (<https://agenda.infn.it/event/32859/>) has been dedicated to present the features of the TIs and the roadmap of SC Magnets for Particle Accelerators, Medical Application and Energy. The second day gave industry the opportunity to present their ideas, projects, suggestions. A dedicated Industry-Research round table on the topic “how the TIs could be useful addressed by Industry” gave the opportunity for frank and constructive discussions among all participants.

Participants and agenda:

The Workshop was organized by a local committee from INFN (G. Bisoffi, D. Giove, A. Liedl, M. Statera) supported by a scientific committee: with the stimulus of the national experts F. Broggi, P. Fabricatore, S. Farinon, U. Gambardella, M. Morandin. R. Musenich, L. Rossi and M. Sorbi, the WP13 steering committee eventually approved the final programme.

The participants list consisted of 32 people both from Companies and Research Institutes with only

two participants by remote.

The Agenda was organized with a first day with presentations by Research Institutes and a second day of presentations by companies with a total Contribution List of 17 talks and one final round table.

The contributions by the Companies were focused on the theme “Interaction with Technological Infrastructure - Innovative Collaboration Projects - Future Developments”

- *ASG Superconductors* - Dr Antonio Pellecchia
- *Bilfinger Noell* - Mr Michael Gehring
- *OCEM PE* - Dr Miguel Pretelli
- *Saes Rial Vacuum* - Dr Carlo Santini
- *Tesla Engineering* - Dr Steve Bates
- *Round Table "The Present and Future Interaction between Industry and Research Institutes"*
- Mauro Morandin (INFN)

Conclusion and Feedback:

All the presentations and the final round table have achieved the aim of the workshop: create an opportunity for a specific community to discussion about the improvements of the collaboration for the future innovative projects.

Beyond the presentation of the specific features of the single TIs and of the competences of the various companies, the discussion and in particular the round table highlighted different points:

Standardization of TI access procedures for companies

The experience gained by light source and neutron source labs can be very valuable since they have setup well established procedures to cope with the services they are providing to industrial users. The IFAST activity in this respect could be carried out in collaboration with LEAPS. To facilitate the interaction and the exploitation of the TIs, it was also discussed to possibly agree on criteria that TIs have to satisfy to be qualified as “capable” of providing services to Industry.

Procurement and TT rules

There is a well perceived impression that the constrains of Technological Transfer (TT) and procurement rules sometimes strongly limit Industry participation to tenders and the opportunities of cooperation. The existing rules seem to reduce the possibilities of addressing, in an efficient and flexible way, the occurrence of unexpected events that are typical of the research environment, such as design modifications, unpredicted extra-costs, etc... Providing an opportunity to collect advance feedbacks from the industrial sector could help TIs in tuning the market survey and organize the tendering procedures to avoid such limitations. Furthermore, the experience of the rules adopted by CERN, or by some non-European states, may be of inspiration. The example of HL-LHC correctors, where the first 6 months could be devoted to design changes and agreement on new tolerances, can be inspiring. A study of the most crucial aspects could be carried out also within the European

projects like IFAST, with the objective to advance concrete proposals.

Test Facilities for HTS Material

HTS material characterization will need ultra-high field test stations (about 30 or 40 T, accessible for significant time spans), variable temperature set-ups, electro-mechanical testing in non-standard configurations (e.g. shear, peel, etc.), variable temperature high current test stations (50 K, 50 kA), background field with variable temperature and high current (15 T, 150 mm, 50 K, 50 kA, this is close to TFD in the US). These Test Facilities required a large investments in terms of funding and qualified personnel: a coordinated approach promoted at the European level by RIs might be important to solicit these large investments and make the best use of them

European industrial leadership position

The European competitiveness in the sector of superconducting magnets at low temperatures may be strongly jeopardized in the evolution towards HTS. The big investments being recently poured by US in the fusion sector and the unique Chinese industrial capabilities are warning alarms. Given the big impact that HTS may have in several key application fields, an initiative at the European level might be the only option to secure the necessary funding needed to implement a large scale ambitious program that can be beneficial for European companies.

Intellectual Property

The actual rules for purely commercial non-R&D work, tend to restrict exploitation of IP, which is not in the interest of the public and private partners in this field. In some countries, agencies exist, which take care of notifying patents to potentially interested industrial companies

TRL levels and Industry

While TRL5-8 is the typical area of collaboration between institutes and companies, lower TRLs imply a higher cost and risk in the RoI. On the other hand, low TRLs is where breakthroughs may lie. Starting to work from TRL1 onwards with the institute is fine for some companies, and too demanding for others. One bottleneck is the bid ruling framework, forbidding companies involved in early-stage prototyping to participate in the construction of the final products. On the other hand, cost estimation for series production is really difficult before the prototyping phase. The “HL-LHC correctors” experience is an example of different paradigm: the Institute provided the ancillary instruments to both the prototype and the series phases: with these premises, the same companies could participate in both development phases.

2.3 PLATFORMS FOR CHARACTERIZATION, TREATMENTS AND TEST OF MATERIALS workshop

This workshop on Platforms for characterization, treatments and test of materials is part of a series of four, each dedicated to a specific category of Technological Platforms (TPs). The present category include platforms for [thermal treatments](#) ; [chemical treatments](#) ; [facilities for surface analyses](#) ; [electromagnetic, mechanical, thermal and associated material characterisation](#) ; [test stations for mechanical manufacturing and tests at cryogenic temperatures](#). The goal was to gather personnel from the labs operating Technological Platforms (TPs) of this type and possible users in particular

from industry, in order to discuss the present exploitation of TPs in operation in the European Institutes.

The platforms that were presented during these days have been created with the aim of testing samples, materials and small components that are then used in the composition of accelerators or magnets. The opening of our platforms to external users is also a way to extend the testing use of our TPs to other fields such as space, aeronautics, climate...

This workshop also gave the opportunity to present Industry needs for their innovative projects and to discuss how these TPs could be better exploited.

Participants and agenda:

The participants list consisted of 26 people both from Companies (5 the first day and 3 the second day) and Research Institutes.

The agenda can be found on the event's indico site:

<https://indico.in2p3.fr/event/28703/timetable/#20230622>

CNRS and CEA Visits:

As part of our workshop focused on 'Platforms for Characterization, Treatments, and Tests of Materials,' we had the opportunity to conduct site visits at both CNRS and CEA. These visits were conducted on separate occasions, and they provided a firsthand look at the infrastructure that are instrumental in advancing our understanding of materials, their properties, and their applications. These platforms are described on the AMICI website: https://amici.ijclab.in2p3.fr/technology_infrastructure/category

At CNRS, we explored cutting-edge laboratories and research centers, including the 'Vacuum Furnace' and the 'Supratech Facility: Cavity Preparation.' The visit to the 'Vacuum Furnace' showcased advanced techniques for materials processing in controlled environments, while the 'Supratech Facility' highlighted capabilities for cavity preparation and characterization.

During our visit to CEA, we had the opportunity to tour a range of specialized platforms, including the 'Vertical Electropolishing Cabinet,' 'Diagnostics, Vacuum and Assembly – DIVA,' 'Test Cryostat at Variable Temperature and High Magnetic Field – CETACES,' 'Characterization Laboratory at Cryogenic Temperature – LABCAF,' 'Pressurized Superfluid Helium Cryostat,' and 'Measurement of the Thermal Conductivity of Insulators and Conductors – MECTIX.' These platforms encompassed a wide spectrum of capabilities, from chemical treatments to cryogenic testing, and provided valuable insights into the cutting-edge research being conducted in the field of materials science.

Workshop facts – discussion with the industrials:

FIRST SESSION:

Many topics were discussed with the industry representatives present at the workshop during this first session. The main conclusions of these exchanges were:

Collaboration between Labs and Industry

This discussion highlights the importance of collaboration between public research laboratories and industry for the execution of complex projects. The role of government agencies in producing pre-designs was acknowledged but it is necessary to determine which parts of the project can be outsourced while maintaining adequate control.

Measurement of Success and Objectives

The importance of defining clear success indicators and integrating them into decision-making and behaviour was emphasized. Additionally, the distinction between fundamental research and applied research was highlighted, each having its own goals and methods for measuring success.

Industry-University Collaboration

This discussion underscores the necessity of strengthening ties between companies and universities, exploring various forms of collaboration. Adapting existing infrastructure and resources to meet industry needs is important. The challenge of attracting companies from different fields was underlined.

Training Highly Qualified Personnel

Training highly qualified personnel is crucial for research and industry, but it is necessary to find effective ways to provide this training, considering time constraints and productivity in the industry.

Infrastructure Mutualization

Mutualizing infrastructures can allow for more efficient resource utilization and increased collaboration among various stakeholders and is therefore encouraged.

SECOND SESSION:

The discussion centered on the dynamics of industry-public research laboratory collaboration, particularly within the context of the Innovate UK agency established at UKRI, pre-design contracts, and the AMICI network.

Collaboration between industry and public research bodies

This discussion highlights how companies interact with public research bodies to address their innovation needs. Collaboration between the private sector and the government is essential to support technological research and development. The example of Innovate UK, created by UKRI in response to companies, which expressed the need for a dedicated contact point within research government bodies to facilitate communication and cooperation, was presented. Requests from companies are sent to this contact point, which then assesses the possibility of responding to the demand. Each UKRI department typically has around ten individuals responsible for handling business-related matters.

Collaboration Between Laboratories

Collaboration between laboratories is a crucial element in fostering innovation. The AMICI Network, which facilitates the exchange of human resources between laboratories, is a concrete example of this collaboration. It was also mentioned that cooperation at the European level can enhance the position of laboratories in the face of global competition.

Importance of Networking and Communication

This discussion underscores the importance of communication networks to facilitate the exchange of information and resources among laboratories. It also highlights the need for continuous evolution of laboratories to meet the changing needs of industry and research. With ten laboratories involved in the network, it was suggested that a common agreement could be established, allowing industrial partners to collaborate with the entire network.

Conclusion:

In summary, the discussions during the workshop highlighted the importance of collaboration between laboratories, industry, and universities, the need to define clear success indicators, and the requirement for training qualified personnel to address technological challenges. The mutualization of infrastructure also emerged as an opportunity for more efficient resource utilization. These key points can serve as a foundation for guiding future recommendations and actions in the field of technological infrastructure.

The discussions also addressed collaboration between the private sector, government, and research laboratories, cooperation among laboratories to respond to demands, and the importance of communication networks to facilitate these collaborations. These elements emphasize the importance of coordination and cooperation in the field of technological infrastructure.

2.4 FACILITIES FOR BEAM TEST OF ACCELERATOR COMPONENTS WORKSHOP

The present category include the beam test facilities at AMICI laboratories used to perform the experimental validation and research vital to advancing the accelerator technology.

The purpose of the workshop was to bring together personnel from scientific laboratories and industrial companies that prepare components used in devices exposed to different types of ionizing radiation, i.e. components used in the construction of large research accelerator facilities, in the construction of medical devices for radiation therapy, devices operating in high radiation fields (e.g. nuclear fusion reactors), and those intended for use in space. The workshop aimed to identify the need for testing the radiation resistance of non-silicon electronic components and to determine changes in the physical properties of structural materials used in the construction of radiation-exposed equipment. The use of new materials, including new composite materials, adhesives and epoxy resins, polymer optical fibers, 3D printed components in the construction of equipment and apparatus exposed to radiation has become increasingly widespread. During the workshop the possibility of testing of components and structural materials in laboratories with the capacity to beam test the physical parameters of materials was presented.

The meeting also formulated the expectations and identified the opportunities for cooperation in the following R&D tasks:

- The influence of low-energy particles on the properties of polymers and adhesives;
- The influence of radiation on the properties of accelerator elements that were created with use of 3D printing;
- The influence of radiation on mechanical properties of nanostructured amorphous-ceramic and metal composites;

- The influence of radiation on the resistance of cable dielectric materials/insulation materials;
- The effect of radiation on the properties of resins used in materials.

Participants and Agenda:

The participants list consisted of 29 people from both Companies, Technological Agencies and Research Institutes.

The agenda can be found on the event's indico site: <https://indico.ifj.edu.pl/event/1122/>

IFJ PAN Visit:

As part of our workshop focused on **Facilities for beam test of accelerator components** we had the opportunity to conduct site visits at AIC-144, a cyclotron-based beam test infrastructure at IFJ PAN. We had opportunity to tour all parts of this infrastructure both cyclotron and two test stations. This visits provided a firsthand look at the one of the infrastructure that is vital in the experimental validation and research vital to the accelerator technology.

This platform is described on the AMICI website:

https://amici.ijclab.in2p3.fr/technology_infrastructure/ifj_pan/test_beam_facilities

Workshop facts:

The topics discussed at the workshop and the main outcomes were:

The evolution of radiation damages in materials applied at cryogenic temperatures

This discussion highlights the importance of scientific support of users in understanding the results of irradiation tests. The collaboration between public research laboratories and industry for the execution of complex projects is vital but the distinction between fundamental research and applied research was highlighted.

Facilities for beam tests

The importance of standardizing of dose rate measurements was highlighted. Not all facilities use the detecting setups which can be compared. Some investments is needed to upgrade the AMICI beam test facilities. Also training of highly qualified personnel is crucial for research and industry. It is necessary to find an effective way to provide this training.

Case Study

Two case study were presented. The first case study was related to sealing material which should withstands extreme irradiation and thermal conditions. The discussion was focused on supporting of users with finding the right irradiation infrastructure in order to obtain required dose rate. The existing databases with irradiation facilities are not disseminated efficiently. The second case study was focused on irradiation methodology and needs of unification of main irradiation procedures.

Industry feedback and roundtable

The discussion was focused on the challenges in establishing of industry and public research laboratory collaboration. The collaboration between the private sector and the public sector is essential to support technological research and development. There are strong demand from industry

as well as laboratory user for support from beam test facilities in order to define the initial beam test setups or for assistance in adaptation of existing test setups in to fulfill test requirements. Also mutualizing infrastructures can allow to fulfill irradiation requirements. Collaboration between beam test facilities is also crucial in fostering innovation. In order to facilitate the exchange of services and resources among laboratories a communication networks would be beneficial and a common agreement could be established, allowing industrial partners to collaborate with the entire network.

Conclusion

The beam test facilities at AMICI laboratories (IFJ PAN, INFN-LNL, INFN-INF, and STFC) are a solid base for the testing of accelerator components, among which beam diagnostics and electronic components, and studies related to materials under irradiation, which can be important for other domains such as space and medical applications. Some new trends in associated R&D have been identified, which call for at least the long-term preservation of these facilities and their upgrading.

2.4.1 Conclusion

This series of workshops served as a pivotal gathering, bringing together key experts from various Test Facilities and industrial partners. It fostered closer connections and facilitated invaluable discussions between institutes, leading to a more profound understanding of TF capabilities and research project requirements. In the weeks and months that followed, it was evident that a more direct exchange between partners had evolved.

The discussions during the workshops underscored the critical significance of collaboration among laboratories, industry, and universities. It emphasized the need to establish clear success indicators and the necessity for training qualified personnel to address technological challenges. The shared use of infrastructure emerged as an opportunity for more efficient resource utilization, laying the groundwork for future recommendations and actions in the realm of technological infrastructure.

The deliberations also addressed collaboration between the private sector, government entities, and research laboratories, promoting cooperation among laboratories to meet demands, and highlighting the pivotal role of communication networks in facilitating these partnerships. These elements underscore the importance of coordination and cooperation.

References

[1] AMICI – Accelerator and Magnets Infrastructure for Cooperation and Innovation – H2020
Grant agreement #731086

[2] EURO-LABS – EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Science, Grant Agreement No
101057511 (EURO-LABS)

Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AMICI	Accelerator and Magnet Infrastructure for Cooperation and Innovation
TF	Technological Facility
TP	Technical Platform